

EXPLORING THE CHRONICLES OF NON-MATHEMATICS MAJOR TEACHERS TEACHING MATHEMATICS: A PHENOMENOLOGY

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Exploring the Chronicles of Non-Mathematics Major Teachers Teaching Mathematics: A Phenomenology

Marjorie M. Moral,* Elealeh S. Timosa
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This phenomenology study aimed to explore and understand the lived experiences of non-mathematics major teachers teaching mathematics. Using purposive sampling, the participating 14 non-mathematics major teachers teaching mathematics from the different public schools around the Division of Davao del Norte were identified. All of them participated in the in-depth interviews. Results revealed the experiences of the participants: facing challenges in curriculum content and resources; gaining new knowledge with mathematical skills; taking pride in perseverance and resourcefulness; and being committed to continuous learning. In response to the challenges they have encountered, they deemed the following coping strategies essential: finding inspiration to teach by students' enthusiasm for learning; preparing diverse resources for student engagement; adapting and consulting references to improve teaching mathematics; and engaging to self-care and stress relief strategies. Upon reflecting on their entire experience, they arrived at the following insights: embrace growth through learning and adaptation; teaching requires mutual effort from both teachers and students; remain flexible and adaptable; stay resilient and determined amidst challenges; find joy in teaching and value in teaching mathematics; and implementation of trainings and seminars. The results of this study were anticipated to be meaningful and important to the participants, teachers, students, and researchers.

Keywords: *non-mathematics major teachers, mathematics, phenomenology approach, qualitative, Philippines*

Introduction

The lived meaning of teaching defines teachers and their lived experiences in the classroom are starting points of 'being a teacher'. But what if these teachers are assigned to teach a subject out of their specialization? Teaching is considered to be the mother of all professions, without teachers, there would be no other professions around. Because of the nobility of the profession, a number of students prefer to take education courses in college. It has been observed that Mathematics is a major in education course which has the least number of enrollees or graduates. That is why, there are many teachers who are non-Mathematics majors handling and teaching the subject in their respective schools (Wagner & Okeke, 2019).

In connection, there is an issue in Australia, according to the report of the Australian Council for Educational Research, twenty-six percent (26%) of the teachers who have been teaching Years 7–10 are teaching outside their expertise. Similarly, in Washington, USA, the number of teachers assigned to teach subjects that do not match their education keeps on escalating, although almost all of them hold at least basic qualifications. Also, out-of-field teaching has worsened slightly in recent years, regardless of plenty of changes focused on enhancing teacher quality. (Weldon, 2019; Ingersoll, 2018; Sambe, 2015)

A cross-sectional study conducted in the Philippines, found that out-of-field teaching is an important but long-unrecognized issue in schools and in the Department of Education in general. This might be due to the fact that the department might have practiced it over time and may not have implemented reforms on the concerns of out-of-field teaching among DepEd schools in the country. Over the past decade, various studies, commissions, and national reports have bemoaned the qualifications and quality of teachers. However, the issue that has hampered their search for high-quality education is partly due to the vast number of teacher-education graduates who major in such subjects, as well as the great number of teachers engaged to teach subjects other than their own field of specialization. (Caylao, 2020)

There is a large research vacuum in the study of non-major in mathematics instructors' mathematics instruction, especially when looking at it from a phenomenological angle. Previous research (e.g., Ball, Thames, & Phelps, 2008) has mostly concentrated on the credentials and effectiveness of math instructors with a background in mathematical education. The lived experiences, difficulties, and coping strategies of educators who do not study in mathematics but yet find themselves in the classroom, however, are not well studied. This gap is important because knowledge of these instructors' viewpoints may help create support networks and professional development plans that are specific to their requirements. Better teaching practices and better student results can result from a greater comprehension of the pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) that these teachers are expected to possess, claims Shulman (2018).

Furthermore, the role of non-mathematics major instructors in providing high-quality mathematics teaching becomes even more relevant given the growing emphasis on STEM education. Schönfeld's (2019) research sheds light on the challenges these educators have in sustaining their students' engagement and proficiency in mathematics. There are, however, few phenomenological studies that explore their career and personal tales. Such research may shed important light on their identities, methods of training, and mental and emotional processes. This knowledge may eventually contribute to improved educational results in mathematics by bridging the knowledge gap between subject matter experts and efficient teaching methods.

Research Questions

This study looked into the chronicles of non-mathematics major teachers teaching mathematics. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of non-mathematics major teachers in mathematics education?
2. What challenges do these teachers face in teaching mathematics?
3. What strategies do non-mathematics major teachers employ to enhance their effectiveness in teaching mathematics?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilizes a qualitative research design using a phenomenological approach in exploring the chronicles of non-mathematics major teachers teaching mathematics. According to Crossman (2020), qualitative research is a type of social science research that collects and manipulates non-numeric data to extract meaning from it and to better understand social life through the study of specific groups or places. It is something to do. It is often framed in contrast to quantitative research, which uses statistical operations to determine cause-and-effect relationships and correlations between variables and uses numerical data to identify large-scale trends. Qualitative research is used in this study. This is because quantitative research typically aims to uncover the underlying meanings and interpretations behind the behaviors and outcomes measured. In contrast to quantitative research, which focuses on numerical data and statistical analysis, qualitative research is concerned with symbolic, interpretive, and relational aspects of social life. Therefore, the researchers in this study examined the experiences, perspectives, and coping mechanisms of non-Mathematics teachers teaching mathematics context.

Phenomenological approaches, on the other hand, are used to understand and identify phenomena based on the perspective of an actor embedded in a particular situation. This study used a phenomenological approach to investigate the behavior of non-mathematics teachers who teach mathematics. Phenomenology is the study of the structure of consciousness as experienced in the first person. The basic structure of experience is its purpose, or the fact that it is directed toward something, since it is an experience of or about something. Experience is directed towards an object by its content or meaning and represents the object in combination with the necessary conditions of realization (Smith, 2017).

In this study, phenomenological approach is used because it is highly appropriate in this context. Given that the study sought to account for the chronicles of non-mathematics major teachers teaching mathematics who participated in this study, it is understood that a phenomenological examination is required in the research context. Initially, phenomenology might be described as the study of experience structures or awareness. Furthermore, phenomenology is the study of conscious experience as it is viewed from the subjective or first-person point of view.

Participants

The participants of the study are the non-Mathematics teachers teaching mathematics at different municipalities in Davao del Norte. In this research project, 14 students were purposely selected. The fourteen (14) participants were from different municipalities in Davao del Norte in accordance with the criterion of the study. Fourteen (14) participants are subjected to in-depth interviews (IDI), with the researcher interviewing each of them individually.

This is in accordance with the recommendation of Creswell (2013) who determined that the ideal number of participants in a qualitative study is between 3 and 15. By including this group of participants in a qualitative research study, data saturation was achieved during the data collection process.

Following the selection of participants, snowball sampling were used to ensure that only those who can provide the necessary data can take part in the study.

Snowball sampling were used, and it is heavily reliant on a set of inclusion criteria. In qualitative research, snowball sampling is a non-probability sampling method where new units are recruited by other units to form part of the sample. Snowball sampling can be a useful way to conduct research about people with specific traits who might otherwise be difficult to identify (e.g., people with a rare disease). Also known as chain sampling or network sampling, snowball sampling begins with one or more study participants. It then continues on the basis of referrals from those participants. This process continues until you reach the desired sample, or a saturation point. Although there are numerous purposeful sampling strategies, criterion sampling appears to be the most commonly used in implementation research.

Combining sampling strategies, on the other hand, may be more appropriate to the goals of implementation research and more consistent with recent advances in quantitative methods (Palinkas et al., 2017, Nikolopoulou K., 2022).

The participants of this study were selected based on the following criteria: (1) the participants must be non-Mathematics major teachers residing here at Davao del Norte; (2) must be non-Mathematics major graduates; (3) and, all participants are treated equally, regardless of their gender preference or identity.

Procedure

To begin with, the researcher undergoes a meticulous manuscript review by the research technical panel. Subsequently, after gaining approval from all panel members, the researcher crafted a permission letter addressed to the relevant institution to seek permission to conduct the study. To inform the selected participants, the researcher will notify them through messages, such as email or any other mutually acceptable means, inviting them to participate in an interview based on their willingness and convenience.

To gather data for this research, the researcher conducted in-depth interviews with participants who were given the freedom to express themselves in Filipino, Bisaya, English, or a combination of these three languages. Prior to the interviews, the researcher seeks the participants' consent regarding recording their responses using recording devices such as smartphones or tape recorders. This was done to ensure that the conversation was accurately captured, and no essential details are missed.

The researchers aimed to obtain valuable and precise information by formulating targeted questions and considering a range of possible responses during the interview. To prevent digressions, questionnaires were prepared to guide the participants. The questions in the interview guide were scrutinized by a panel of experts to ensure that they were aligned with the study's themes.

Additionally, the researcher carefully documented all the participants' choices and feedback to provide pertinent information to the study. The researcher prioritizes the confidentiality of the participants by storing the data in password-protected files. Maintaining confidentiality was a crucial step for the researcher in this study to guarantee the safeguarding of the participants' personal information.

Data Analysis

The data gathered in this research were presented and analyzed in this study based on the needs and objectives of this research endeavor. This implies that sufficient analysis of the content of the participant's responses was performed to generate the study's findings. Therefore, data analysis aims the process of inspecting, cleansing, transforming, and modeling data in order to discover useful information, propose conclusions, and support decision-making. In addition, the data analysis goal is to generate knowledge about common patterns and themes in human experience, this process is repeated with each new interview or account until all have been compared.

Qualitative data analysis is a systematic process of examining and organizing various forms of data, such as interview transcripts and observation notes, to gain a deeper understanding of a particular phenomenon. This process can be challenging and time-consuming, as the researcher aims to uncover the underlying meanings behind participants' actions and reactions. Despite the availability of advanced analysis technologies, the researcher is still the primary instrument in extracting these meanings through deep engagement with the data and participants. Although different qualitative methodologies may have different approaches, the basic phases of content analysis remain consistent, including data preparation, reading and reflection, coding, categorizing, and developing themes (Ravidran, 2019).

Firstly, a snowball sampling strategy was used to begin the data collection procedure. Participants in this process are identified through observation; fourteen (14) non-Mathematics major teachers takes part in the research. They sign a consent form, indicating their agreement to the conditions and that their participation in the study indicates that they are willing to share their knowledge and experience, which be extremely useful for the study.

The key participants were individually briefed on the project prior to the interview, which aims to gather data for the study. The interview commenced with an introduction, followed by an overview of the meeting's objectives and scope, including confidentiality and duration. The participants are also informed in detail about the recording process and the technical aspects involved, as well as the reasons why the meeting was recorded.

Ethical Considerations

The ethical codes are in place to ensure a pleasant scientific practice in research the importance of this study was placed on how it was observed and applied to the informants, as well as the setting that concerns both the participants' and the researchers' agreement. Furthermore, the key concerns of this study were persons with whom the researcher had no relationship. As a result, the researcher secured their safety and provides them with complete protection so that they do not lose interest.

As a result, it is the researcher's primary responsibility to safeguard their safety and provide them with complete protection so that they do not lose trust. The researcher followed the following ethical guidelines for conducting the study: respect for persons, beneficence, justice, confidentiality, and consent (Boyatzis, 1998; Mack et al., 2005).

Respect for Person necessitates a researcher's commitment not to take advantage of the research participants' flaws in order to maintain friendship, trust, and confidence among the participants and the researcher, self-sufficiency should be avoided. A letter was written to the informed consent form for the participants ahead of time. The letter were designed to tell anyone who will be interested, namely the administrators of the participants' schools, universities, and colleges, about the study's progress. This will be done out of respect for the people involved in the study (Creswell, 2012).

During the process of this research, I developed courtesy and connection with my participants. I obtained their permission before

documenting the IDI session. I previously permitted them to ask inquiries at any moment, before, during, and after the interviews. Moreover, I persist and really emphasize to them that all of the impending IDI sessions to be highly classified are concealed from the general public.

Beneficence needs a commitment to reducing the members' risks rather than increasing the income owed to them. To avoid putting any participant at risk, the interviewee's identity were kept anonymous. Participants were protected at all times, and no file of information would be left unattended or unsecured (Bricki & Green, 2007). During the conduct of this research, I the researcher employ pseudonyms to protect the participants' identities, so that the sources of statements and responses will not be revealed. In addition, the interview guide questions avoided any sensitive or unimportant topics that would made the participants feel anxious. I the researcher assures that no participants expressed any discomfort while answering interview questions during the course of the study.

Justice as part of the process, a sensible allocation of risks and benefits is required as a result of the study's findings. It is very important to acknowledge the contributions of all participants as they generally become part of the success of the research. In all of their attempts, they must be given appropriate credit. During the interview, they were unable to spend any money. As a gesture of appreciation for their efforts in the study, they were also given practical gifts (Crabtree and Bloom, 2006).

During the conduct of this research, I gladly treat my participants with legitimacy and equality. As result, the benefits were distributed equitably to all participants as well as the risks that this research may demand. Preferably I make sure that all the participants where comfortable in dealing with and participating in this research. Furthermore, as compensation for the participants' effort and presence, I gave them practical gifts and tokens.

Confidentiality is both the direction and protection of results and conclusions. A coding system was used to track participants. Participants' identities were kept confidential. After data analysis, all materials, including tapes, coded notes, etc., should be destroyed. Some informants were initially reluctant to be interviewed because they did not know what to say. However, after the researcher assured them that their responses would be treated as confidential, they ultimately agreed to be interviewed and appeared relaxed when answering the interview questions (Marie and Van Der Westhuizen, 2007).

Consent is another important approach to showing people that you are interested in conducting research. This is done to make participants aware of the goals and objectives of the research study in which they are participating. Written permission was provided to obtain their consent. Once they received confirmation, they were asked to participate in in-depth interviews. Of course, I will keep you informed of the research results (Creswell, 2012).

As a result, I created a survey to respect the participants by asking them if they wanted to participate in this study. Additionally, an information letter was sent to participants informing them of the data collection process and informing them that the information collected in the study was fully protected. Finally, all participants who chose not to participate in the study were given the opportunity to decline their participation with a promise to maintain the confidentiality of their data after the study ended.

Results and Discussion

This section was divided into four parts: Part one discussed the data collected from participants, from which the qualitative data were derived. Part two covered data analysis procedures and the steps in categorizing emergent themes from in-depth interviews. Part three dealt with the responses to the interview questions under each research problem. Lastly part four was a summary of the responses.

Participants

The participants of this study were the non-mathematics major teachers teaching mathematics around the Division of Davao del Norte. As shown in Table 1, a total of 14 individuals took part in this study, comprising 14 participants for the in-depth interview.

In-depth Interview. There were fourteen key participants in this study. All of these participants were non-mathematics major teachers teaching mathematics around the Division of Davao del Norte. To uphold the principle of confidentiality, each participant was assigned a pseudonym during the in-depth interview, following the approach employed by Bernal (2014). These pseudonyms were chosen by the participants themselves based on their preferences and the unique characteristics that emerged during the interview sessions.

The selected pseudonyms provided insight into the characteristics and qualities of the participants. For instance, Joyful earned his nickname due to the joyfulness that he portrays during the interview. Happy was named for her personality that she always portrays when teaching. Traditional was chosen for the participant who uses traditional methods during teaching the students. Writer received his nickname due to the work that is given to him by the DepEd as the Division Writer. Chill earned his nickname due to his chillness during teaching the students, did not embrace stress while teaching, and ensuring that the environment of the classroom is always chill. Agronomist was named for her since she is an Agricultural Economist. Pretty was chosen for the participant who is pretty, inside and out as a teacher.

Furthermore, Soft voice received her nickname due to the calmness and softness of her voice when she is talking. Achiever earned her nickname since she is already achieving her dreams at an early age. Scientist was chosen for the participant who majored in science who embraced and love math along her journey in teaching. Dynamic was chosen for the participant who skillfully juggled his busy

schedules while still prioritizing teaching and learning. Caring received her nickname due to her caringness towards her students. Serious earned his nickname due to the seriousness he portrays while teaching. Lastly, Angel was the pseudonym for another participant because of her angelic face and voice.

Table 1. *Participants of the Study*

<i>In-Depth Interview (Pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Code</i>
Joyful	28	Male	IDI-1
Happy	39	Female	IDI-2
Traditional	55	Female	IDI-3
Writer	46	Male	IDI-4
Chill	44	Male	IDI-5
Agronomist	37	Female	IDI-6
Pretty	24	Female	IDI-7
Soft voice	30	Female	IDI-8
Achiever	24	Female	IDI-9
Scientist	36	Female	IDI-10
Dynamic	34	Male	IDI-11
Caring	36	Female	IDI-12
Serious	25	Male	IDI-13
Angel	27	Female	IDI-14
Total = 14			

All participants answered the same set of questions. The selection of participants was based on their involvement and experiences as a non-mathematics teacher teaching mathematics, which were identified by the researcher and verified through personal declarations provided by the participants.

The in-depth interview was conducted face-to-face for it to be more personal and engaging, allowing for deeper insights and better interpretation of non-verbal cues. Additionally, immediate clarification and follow-up questions can be addressed, fostering a more comprehensive understanding of the participant's experiences. Most of the participants did ask for a softcopy and hardcopy which was distributed to their respective schools as per request. The researcher respected the participant's decision when asked to adjust and reschedule the interview due to their important reasons related to their work. The researcher did consider face-to-face as an important factor to consider in achieving and ensuring the validity and credibility of the study.

Categorization of Data

After conducting in-depth interviews, the interview responses were transcribed, translated, and analyzed. The analysis commenced with the coding process, which involved organizing the materials into segments of texts to derive meaningful information. Through coding, descriptions of the participants' settings and thematic categories were generated to shape an overall depiction of the phenomenon under study. Data results were presented in the form of a table. This data gathered was handed to the data analyst for analysis of data and emerging themes.

The data was categorized into central themes based on the research questions, and these themes were presented. Thorough discussions were conducted to vividly describe the emerged themes from the study, while the core ideas of the participants' responses were also included in the table alongside the major themes.

In the data analysis, we followed the second step by categorizing the data and presenting it in Table 2. The themes were organized according to the research questions and referred to as central themes, while the opposing significant themes were represented as co-ideas from the participants' responses. Additionally, the table included a column indicating the frequency of the responses, which served as the basis for classifying them into general, typical, and variant categories, as discussed above.

Research Question No. 1: What are the experiences of non-mathematics major teachers teaching mathematics?

To answer this research question, in-depth interviews were conducted with the participants, respectively. Hence, several sub-questions were asked to understand their experiences regarding the language they used in mathematics teaching.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 1 were presented in Table 2. From the answers of the participants, four major themes had emerged: facing challenges in curriculum content and resources, gaining new knowledge with mathematical skills, taking pride in perseverance and resourcefulness, and being committed to continuous learning.

Facing Challenges in Curriculum Content and Resources

The theme focuses on the challenges of the teachers about how to deliver well and follow the curriculum and content knowledge of math subject. The participants highlight the challenges they have experience in their journey on teaching mathematics. Moreover, they

feel incompetent and struggle to effectively deliver difficult math terms and explanations during teaching. The pressure to teach the lesson to the students about things that they are not that familiar with, creates confusion and hesitation, as they fear that they may not be able to properly explain concepts and that it could confuse their students. According to Joyful (pseudonym), he said that he cannot thoroughly follow the curriculum guide and he cannot deliver some topics well. He stated that:

Table 2. *Non-Mathematics Major Teachers Teaching Mathematics' Experiences*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Facing Challenges in Curriculum Content and Resources	<p>"I cannot thoroughly follow the curriculum guide that is set forth by the department. This is because there are some topics that I cannot deliver well, because I am not that good in mathematics." – IDI-01</p> <p>"There were many challenges in teaching mathematics, especially when you are not a mathematics major. First is the curriculum itself, the lessons. Although during college days, it feels like you've reviewed those topics before. Even though the curriculum may have changed, some lessons remain the same. However, the most challenging part is when you encounter the new curriculum, the ones we didn't have during our time." – IDI-04</p> <p>"There are lots of challenges I encountered in teaching mathematics, since I am not a mathematics major, but a science major. I need to study in advance since I am not familiar with the topic." – IDI-10</p> <p>"Okay, some of the challenges are the terminologies that are hard to pronounce or understand, and some formulas that I'm not familiar with and find difficult to understand." – IDI-11</p> <p>"One of my challenges during that time is, there are complex concepts that I don't understand, so I struggle to teach my students, to explain to them in a way that they can easily understand, because it's also very difficult for me to comprehend how to deliver that topic. Especially those difficult concepts in math." – IDI-13</p>
Gaining New Knowledge with Mathematical Skills	<p>"There are also many positive things about being a non-mathematics major teaching mathematics. Like, along the way, you will learn a lot of things." – IDI-08</p> <p>"Okay, so positive things. So, first would be, you will be able to learn new things." – IDI-09</p> <p>"Okay, the positive things are I learned new things, especially in math." – IDI-10</p> <p>"One of the positive things is, I learned some techniques on how to solve some problems using other formulas." – IDI-11</p> <p>"I've learned some techniques on how to solve problems. I also learn basic concepts, like fundamental math concepts." – IDI-13</p> <p>"By teaching math as a non-math major, you will learn new things, many things about math. Your learnings about math will go further your limits. You will learn some techniques on how to solve some problems that are new to you." – IDI-14</p>
Taking Pride in Perseverance and Resourcefulness	<p>"I'm very proud even though I'm not a mathematics major, but I embraced the challenge of teaching mathematics." – IDI-01</p> <p>"Proud of the behavior of the learners during that time. Although I am not a mathematics major, but I can see based on the assessment I gave them, that they have learned." – IDI-04</p> <p>"There are now many professionals. And the reason is just mathematics. I have a major in math teacher now in Tagum, there are many of them now. That's what makes me proud. Because if you didn't teach math, if you didn't try, maybe they wouldn't be like that, maybe. But at least you're proud that you are part of their lives, why they succeeded." – IDI-05</p> <p>"I can say that I'm proud because math isn't easy. So I'm proud to be a non-mathematics graduate but I teach math because not everyone can understand math immediately. I'm also proud of the fact that they have learned something from me." – IDI-07</p> <p>"I am most proud of when, earlier, I mentioned that some of my students will say that my teaching and delivery are nice. At the same time, they will say they understand. I am proud that my students are learning, and I can see that their assessment results as well as their exams and grades are getting higher." – IDI-08</p> <p>"Most proud of, perhaps because I was able to deliver my lessons well. And then I learned that I am capable of teaching even different subjects, even though that is not my thing." – IDI-09</p> <p>"I am most proud of when I see the students achieving high scores in activities and enjoying themselves." – IDI-10</p> <p>"The best and most proud moment for a teacher who teaches mathematics without being a mathematics major is seeing their learners learn from them, despite the challenges." – IDI-12</p> <p>"I am very proud even though I am not a math major, I am proud because I managed to teach to my students the thing that is not my field. I am also proud that some students appreciated my efforts." – IDI-14</p>
Being Committed to Continuous Learning	<p>"The character is perseverant. I really want to study. I keep studying about it so I can deliver what the kids really need to learn." – IDI-01</p> <p>"It molds me to be resourceful, not just as an individual but also as a teacher, not only in mathematics but also in other subjects that I teach." – IDI-02</p> <p>"You have to study, even if you're good at it. Even if you're a math major, you have to study. You just have to study. You just have to learn well, and then you have to create something that's more attractive to the children to motivate them." – IDI-05</p> <p>"So, for further references, I go to the library, you know. As long as there are references, it's okay. So, I use the library and also utilize YouTube, you know, the internet." – IDI-06</p> <p>"I've learned that I am someone who is able to learn new things. I am very open-minded when it comes to learning</p>

new things.” – IDI-09

“I did realize that I am resourceful. I realized that I wasn't confident in this area, but because I needed to teach, and there were no other teachers available here, so I was forced to do it myself because we only have one math major here and several sections. So, I realized, 'Oh, I'm resourceful'.” – IDI-10

“Okay, so what I perceived as my character as a non-mathematics teacher teaching math is that I've become studious. Meaning, I've become diligent in studying what needs to be taught in math.” – IDI-13

“Okay, as I teach math or as I go along teaching math, I realized that I'm a very hardworking and studious person. I do research, any kind of research, just to find the exact answer to the problem I've encountered in math.” – IDI-14

“I cannot thoroughly follow the curriculum guide that is set forth by the department. Ah because there are some topics that I cannot deliver well because I am not that good in mathematics.” (IDI-01)

(I cannot thoroughly follow the curriculum guide that is set forth by the department. This is because there are some topics that I cannot deliver well, because I am not that good in mathematics.)

As with another participant, Writer (pseudonym) said that the curriculum itself is hard to understand because it is constantly changing. He stated that:

“So, ah daghang challenges, there are so many challenges in teaching mathematics, especially you are non-major in mathematics. First, is the curriculum itself, the lessons. But, although during the college days, high school days parang na review mo na kase, lection nimo sauna. As long as nga na change man tuod ang curriculum, pero naa pay mga lessons nga nabalik. But ang pinaka challenging katong naapil sa new curriculum, nga wala na nato naabtan during our time” – (IDI-04)

(“There were many challenges in teaching mathematics, especially when you are not a mathematics major. First is the curriculum itself, the lessons. Although during college days, it feels like you've reviewed those topics before. Even though the curriculum may have changed, some lessons remain the same. However, the most challenging part is when you encounter the new curriculum, the ones we didn't have during our time.”)

As with Scientist (pseudonym), she stated that since she is a science major, there are lots of challenges that she encountered. She needs to study in advance since she is not familiar with the topic, he said:

“There are lots of challenges I encountered in teaching mathematics, since I am not a mathematic major, science major. So, first thing is, I need to study in advance, since I am not familiar with the topic.” (IDI-10)

(There are lots of challenges I encountered in teaching mathematics, since I am not a mathematics major, but a science major. I need to study in advance since I am not familiar with the topic.)

In addition, Dynamic (pseudonym) shared that there are terminologies that are hard to pronounce, and that there are some formulas that he is not familiar with. He stated:

“Okay, ah some of the challenges are ah the terminologies that is hard to pronounce or understand, and some formulas that are not familiar for me to understand.” (IDI-11)

(Okay, some of the challenges are the terminologies that are hard to pronounce or understand, and some formulas that I'm not familiar with and find difficult to understand.)

Lastly, Serious (pseudonym) stated that he struggles to teach complex concepts at his students. He mentioned that he was not able to explain the concepts to his students, because of the difficulty on how to comprehend the topic, he stated:

“So, isa sa akoang challenges jud ato nga time is, kanang being a non-mathematics teacher nga nagtudlo ug math is, naay mga complex concepts nga akoang dili masabtan so maglisod ko ug tudlo sa akoang mga students, kung unsaon ni pagpasabot sa ilaha nga kanang dali ra sila makasabot, tungod kay ah lisod kaayo sabton pud sa ako nga part unsaon ni pagdeliver ni nga topic. Nga kanang mga lisod nag ani nga concept sa math.” (IDI-13)

“One of my challenges during that time is, there are complex concepts that I don't understand, so I struggle to teach my students, to explain to them in a way that they can easily understand, because it's also very difficult for me to comprehend how to deliver that topic. Especially those difficult concepts in math.” – IDI-13)

Gaining New Knowledge with Mathematical Skills

The theme focuses on the positive things that the non-mathematics teachers acquire during teaching. The participants highlight the improvements they have observed in their lives. Thus, they mention the increased of new learning that they gained. According to Soft Voice (pseudonym), there are many positive things about being a non-mathematics major teacher. Based on her experience, she narrated her improvements along the way, mentioning that she has noticed a positive change. She stated that:

“Ah, daghan pud ug mga positive things, noh being a non-mathematics major teaching mathematics. Like kuan, along the way ba, you will learn a lot of things.” (IDI-08)

(There are also many positive things about being a non- mathematics major teaching mathematics. Like, along the way, you will learn a lot of things.)

As with the other participant, Achiever (pseudonym) she shared that by teaching math even though you are not a math major, you will be able to learn new things. She said:

“Okay, so positive things. So, first would be, you will be able to learn new things.” (IDI-09)

(Okay, so positive things. So, first would be, you will be able to learn new things.)

In addition, Scientist (pseudonym) stated also that by teaching math, she also learned new things. She said:

“Okay, the positive things are I learned new things especially in math.” (IDI-10)

(Okay, the positive things are I learned new things, especially in math.)

Moreover, Dynamic (pseudonym) also stated the positive effect on teaching mathematics a non-mathematics major. He said that by teaching math, he learned new techniques on how to solve using new formulas that he encountered, he mentioned:

“One of the positive things is, I learned some techniques on how to solve some problems using other formulas” (IDI-11)

(One of the positive things is, I learned some techniques on how to solve some problems using other formulas.)

Furthermore, Serious (pseudonym) also expressed that he learned new techniques on how to solve new problems. He said also that he learned the basic concepts such as fundamental concepts in math, he stated:

“I learned some techniques on how to solve problems. Naga learn pud kog mga basic concepts, like kanang mga fundamental concepts sa math.” (IDI-13)

(I've learned some techniques on how to solve problems. I also learn basic concepts, like fundamental math concepts.)

Lastly, Angel (pseudonym) explained that as you teach math, you will learn new things. Her knowledge about math had improved. She attributed the enhancement of her learnings about the techniques that she learned, she shared:

“By teaching math as a non-math major, you will learn new things, many things about math. Ahh your learnings about math will go further your limits. You will learn some techniques on how to solve some problems that are new to you” (IDI-14)

(By teaching math as a non-math major, you will learn new things, many things about math. Your learnings about math will go further your limits. You will learn some techniques on how to solve some problems that are new to you.)

Taking Pride in Perseverance and Resourcefulness

The theme explores the fruit of perseverance and resourcefulness of the non- mathematics teacher teaching mathematics. The participants express their proudness about the things that they achieve by teaching math. Some shared that there are now many students that are professionals that is thanking them because of their presence and teaching during the time that they are still studying. Some are proud because of the braveness that they got when teaching the subject that they are not good into. According to Joyful (pseudonym), he is very proud of himself by embracing the challenge of teaching mathematics, even though it is not his major. He said:

“Proud kaayo ko bisan pag dili ko mathematics major pero gikaya nako ba, nga gidawat nako ang challenge to teach mathematics” – (IDI-01)

“I'm very proud even though I'm not a mathematics major, but I embraced the challenge of teaching mathematics.”

Additionally, Writer (pseudonym) expressed his feelings about being proud because of the behavior of his students during his teaching. Writer (pseudonym) highlighted that based on the assessments that he gave to the students, he can conclude that they have learned from him, and that is what makes him proud. He stated:

“Proud of the behavior of the learners during that time noh, na although dili ko mathematics major, pero makita nako based sa ilahang assessment nga gipanghatag nako sa ilaha, nga naka learn sila”. (IDI-04)

(“Proud of the behavior of the learners during that time. Although I am not a mathematics major, but I can see based on the assessment I gave them, that they have learned.”)

As with the other participants, Chill (pseudonym) shares that his students before are now professionals, and it is because of mathematics. He believed that if he did not teach that subject, then maybe, his students before are on the different path now. He is proud because he teaches math to them, he shared:

“Daghan na kaayo uy, daghan na kaayo kog mga professional. Unya kanang ang hinungdan kay mathematics ra. Naa man pud koy major in math nga teacher karon sa Tagum, daghan na sila uy. Mao nay makaproud. Kay kung wala ka nagtudlo ug math, wala to nimo gipaningkamutan, ah dili pud siguro to sila mahimong mga ing ana, maybe. Pero, at least proud jud ka ba nga part ka sa ilahang

life nganong na success sila.” (IDI-05)

(There are now many professionals. And the reason is just mathematics. I have a major in math teacher now in Tagum, there are many of them now. That's what makes me proud. Because if you didn't teach math, if you didn't try, maybe they wouldn't be like that, maybe. But at least you're proud that you are part of their lives, why they succeeded.)

Moreover, Pretty (pseudonym) said that math is not really easy. She shared that math is not the subject that anyone can understand immediately, but despite of that challenge, she is still feeling proud because she teaches it to her students, despite being a non-mathematics major. She is also proud that her students learned from her, she mentioned:

“So, makaingon ko nga proud kayko kay ang math man gud dili siya sayon. So makaingon ko nga proud ko nga maging non-mathematics graduate ko pero nag teach kog math kay ngano, dili tanan dayon makasabot sa math. Naay uban nga maglisod jud sila ug sabot pa nganong naingon-ani ni, kay complicated kaayo ang math. Pero ano, proud lang pud ko sa part nga naa silay natun-an sa akoo.” (IDI-07)

(I can say that I'm proud because math isn't easy. So I'm proud to be a non-mathematics graduate but I teach math because not everyone can understand math immediately. I'm also proud of the fact that they have learned something from me.)

Furthermore, Soft Voice (pseudonym) also stated her proudness on teaching math despite being a non-mathematics major. She emphasized that her students appreciate her teaching and learn from her effectively. This suggested that Soft Voice (pseudonym) shown to her students her way of adapting her teaching approach to ensure effective teaching among them really well, she stated:

“I am most proud of sa katong giingon nako kaganina nga some of my students will gonna say that nice akoang pagtudlo and pag deliver. At the same time, they will understand daw. I am proud that my students are learning, and I can see that their assessment results as well as their exams and grades are getting higher.” (IDI- 08)

In addition, Achiever (pseudonym) expressed her proud feeling because she delivers her lesson well to her students. She also realized that she is capable of teaching different subject. The statement highlighted the experience of Achiever (pseudonym), who might have encountered difficulties in her teaching at first but soon realizes that she can face those challenge well, she said:

“Ahh, most proud of, siguro kay I was able to deliver my lessons well. And then I learned na capable diay ko mutudlo bisag lahi nga subject, even though that is not my thing.” (IDI-09)

(Most proud of, perhaps because I was able to deliver my lessons well. And then I learned that I am capable of teaching even different subjects, even though that is not my thing.)

Moreover, Scientist (pseudonym) expressed that she is proud when her students achieve high scores on the activities that she gives, and that she is proud seeing her students enjoying her lessons. She said:

“I am most proud of, kung makit-an nako sa mga bata nga tag-as ug scores sa mga activities, and makit-an nako nga nag-enjoy sila.” (IDI-10)

Additionally, Caring (pseudonym) also said that the most proud moment for a teacher is to see her students learn from them, despite the challenges that occurs along the way, because she is not a math major teacher, she said:

“Ang pinaka the best jud to become ah ang pinaka maka proud sa teacher nga nag teach ug mathematics nga dili mathematics major is makita niya iyang mga learners nga naka learn sa iyaha, despite sa mga challenges.” (IDI-12)

(The best and most proud moment for a teacher who teaches mathematics without being a mathematics major is seeing their learners learn from them, despite the challenges.)

Lastly, Angel (pseudonym) stated that even though she is not a math major, she is proud because she managed to teach her students the thing that is not her field. This adaptation was necessary because it became significantly more difficult for her to elaborate on the concepts in Math, but she still managed to deliver it well, and she is proud because her students appreciated her efforts, she mentioned:

“I am very proud even though I am not a math major, I am proud because I managed to teach to my students the thing that is not my field. I am also proud that some students appreciated my efforts.” (IDI-14)

(I am very proud even though I am not a math major, I am proud because I managed to teach to my students the thing that is not my field. I am also proud that some students appreciated my efforts.)

Being Committed to Continuous Learning

The theme revolves around the experiences of the commitment of the teachers along the way on teaching mathematics despite being a non-mathematics major teacher. In addition, the participants expressed their feelings and realizations on their experiences teaching math. They come up with some conclusion about what ability they really have inside them. Based on the experience of Joyful (pseudonym), he stated that the character that he concludes that he had in himself is being perseverant. He said that he should study

well about the lessons so that he can deliver it well to his students, he mentioned:

“The character is kanang perseverant. Kanang gusto jud ko mu study jud ba. Kanang sigeg study about sa kana kay para ma deliver jud nako ug unsa man jud galing ang kinahanglan ma tun-an sa mga bata. – (IDI-01)

As with another participant, Happy (pseudonym) stated that by that experience, it molds her to be resourceful, in everything. She said:

“It defines my character, because it molds me to be resourceful, as an individual, as a teacher, not only in mathematics but also in other subjects that I taught” (IDI02)

“(It molds me to be resourceful, not just as an individual but also as a teacher, not only in mathematics but also in other subjects that I teach.”)

In addition, Chill (pseudonym) stated that even if you are good at math, you still need to study. You have to come up with a creative plan on how you can motivate students to learn math with you, he said:

“Study jud, bisan pa’g hawd naka. Bisan pag math major ka, you have to study jud Basta kay magtuon lang ka. Imo lang jud tun an ug maayo, unya magtuon ka tapos you have to create something nga kanang mas attractive bitaw sa mga bata nga para ma motivate.” (IDI-05)

(You have to study, even if you're good at it. Even if you're a math major, you have to study. You just have to study. You just have to learn well, and then you have to create something that's more attractive to the children to motivate them.)

Moreover, Agronomist’s (pseudonym) way of practicing the subject is going to the library, utilizes YouTube, the internet, so that she can be prepared to what she will discuss inside the classroom, she said:

“So, further references, I go on sa mga library. As long as naay references, okay ra. So, library and also gamitan nato ug mga YouTube, mga ing ana, internet.” (IDI-06)

(So, for further references, I go to the library, you know. As long as there are references, it's okay. So, I use the library and also utilize YouTube, you know, the internet.)

Furthermore, Achiever (pseudonym) stated that she realizes that she is someone who are able to learn new things and that she is open-minded when it comes to learning, she said:

“I learned na kanang kuan diay ko nga tao, kana ganing able to learn new things gyud. Kana bang very open- minded to kanang learn new things.” (IDI-09)

“I've learned that I am someone who is able to learn new things. I am very open-minded when it comes to learning new things.” – IDI-09

Additionally, Scientist (pseudonym) shared her realization along the way in teaching math. She strives hard just to be able to teach new learnings to her students, and that is where she realizes that she is resourceful. She stated:

“Ah dire nako na kuan nga resourceful diay ko. Nakit-an nako ba nga, hala uy, dili ko hawod ani unya tungod kay kailangan nako mutudlo kay walay laing mudawat sa mga teachers direa, so ako ang napugos kase isa ra ang among math major dire noh unya pila ka section. So, nakaingon ko nga “hala noh resourceful diay ko.” (IDI- 10)

(I did realize that I am resourceful. I realized that I wasn't confident in this area, but because I needed to teach, and there were no other teachers available here, so I was forced to do it myself because we only have one math major here and several sections. So, I realized, 'Oh, I'm resourceful'.)

As with the other participant, Serious (pseudonym) perceived that he became studious. He became diligent in studying for him to deliver it to his students. This concerns highlight his dedication to fostering effective teaching among his students in the classroom, he shared:

“Akong na perceived nga character as a non- mathematics teacher nga nagtudlo ug math is, studious nako, nahimo nakong studious. Kana ganing gina studihan nako ang mga dapat itudllo sa math. Nga kani nga subject nga akoang e klase ah itudlo sa klase, kay gitudihan nako, and then gapangita ko ug sources nga kanang magamit nako sa pagtudlo sa math.” (IDI-13)

(Okay, so what I perceived as my character as a non- mathematics teacher teaching math is that I've become studious. Meaning, I've become diligent in studying what needs to be taught in math.)

Lastly, Angel (pseudonym) also realized that along with her experience teaching math, she became hardworking and studious person. This suggested that Angel (pseudonym) recognized the importance of adapting this teaching approach to ensure effective teaching can make a fruitful conclusion in the future, she stated:

“Okay, by teaching math or as I go along in teaching math, I realized that I’m very a hardworking and studious person. Hardworking

and studious to the point nga usahay dili nako makatulong sigeg pangita sa right solution sa topic nga akong e discuss. Like I do research, any kind of research just to find the exact answer to the problem that I've encountered in math" (IDI-14)

(Okay, as I teach math or as I go along teaching math, I realized that I'm a very hardworking and studious person. I do research, any kind of research, just to find the exact answer to the problem I've encountered in math.)

Research Question No. 2: How do these non-mathematics major teachers teaching mathematics cope with the challenges they have experienced?

To answer this research question, in-depth interviews were conducted with the participants, respectively. Hence, several sub-questions were asked to understand their experiences regarding the language they used in mathematics teaching.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 2 were presented in Table 3. From the answers of the participants, four major themes had emerged: finding inspiration to teach by students' enthusiasm for learning, preparing diverse resources for student engagement, adapting and consulting references to improve teaching mathematics, and engaging to self-care and stress relief strategies.

Table 3. *Coping Mechanisms for the Challenges Faced by Non-Mathematics Major Teacher Teaching Mathematics*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Finding Inspiration to Teach by Students' Enthusiasm for Learning	<p>"You know, it's like, someone has to be the math teacher because there's no one else to do it (laughs). That's why I teach. But I also get motivated by the kids because I believe it's really necessary for them, especially in the long run." – IDI01</p> <p>"Firstly, even before class starts, when my students ask me, "Sir, what's our topic for today?" or "What's our lesson for today?" it shows that they enjoy learning. That's one of the teaching strategies I implement—to make them love learning mathematics. So, that's what motivates me. The eagerness of the learners." – IDI04</p> <p>"Students. Students who haven't seen how enjoyable mathematics can be. So, motivation comes from the students and their learning that they get from me." – IDI05</p> <p>"Personally, what motivates me to keep going is seeing that my students are learning and knowing that they are not just there to pass time. I want my students to succeed and become contributing members of a loving society." – IDI08</p> <p>"Okay, so the main motivation for why I keep going even though teaching math is very hard, is my students. Why? Because my students rely on me. They are waiting for me to teach them new lessons for them to learn." – IDI14</p>
Preparing Diverse Resources for Student Engagement	<p>"Alright, in mathematics, I consistently utilize PowerPoint presentations and video lessons, especially for topics that are challenging to explain solely through verbal explanation. I find that incorporating video lessons helps to reinforce the concepts effectively." – IDI10</p> <p>"Okay, I study my topics every day before class, even weekends. I used to watch YouTube videos, like tutorials and search my topics on the internet, aside from the books and modules we had." – IDI11</p> <p>"Most of the time, we should have engaging activities such as collaborative learning. The approach should be more student-centered so they can experience and retain the concepts better." – IDI12</p> <p>"Okay, so preparations include studying the lesson I'll be teaching them. I thoroughly study what I'll teach them. Then, I also prepare the materials I'll use for teaching. I also ensure that my lesson plan is ready, usually preparing it a week before the class. Along with the activities, I organize what activities I'll use for teaching that particular lesson or topic." – IDI13</p> <p>"Preparations involve studying my topics every day, especially at night before my class, and particularly on weekends when I have more time to study. I watch video tutorials on YouTube and search for my topics on the internet. Additionally, I review the modules beforehand to ensure I'm prepared for what to discuss in class. Another aspect is preparing my lesson plans before I engage in class." – IDI14</p>
Adapting and Consulting References to Improve Teaching Mathematics	<p>"I didn't have difficulty in adapting since we're educators, right? So, it's also said that changes are constant. So, we're open to that. We won't just say, we'll just stay inside this box." – IDI04</p> <p>"My preparation involves studying and consulting various references. If there's something I can't grasp, I ask those who are majoring in math, the experts." – IDI05</p> <p>As a first-time non-mathematics teacher teaching mathematics, adapting was a learning process along the way. With the help of my co-teachers, especially Sir Fred, who is a mathematics major, I would ask him questions like, 'Sir, how should I deliver this? What are some nice examples for these variables and constants in algebraic expressions?' He would give me tips. So, I adapted gradually through this process." – IDI08</p> <p>"I ask for help from other teachers, especially those who are math majors like me. If I'm feeling very stressed because I don't know how to handle something, I go to them and say, 'Hey, can you help me with this? I'm not sure what to do.' I ask for their help so that the burden becomes lighter, and I no longer stress about that topic because I now understand. I seek the assistance of my colleague." – IDI10</p> <p>I always asks questions or advise to some of my colleagues that is expert in mathematics. I am open to any suggestions, clarifications, and comments from my colleagues." – IDI11</p> <p>"I ask for help from other teachers, especially those who are math majors like me. You can ask for help so that you won't stress about how to deliver it to your learners. So, let's seek, let's ask for help, it's not bad to seek help from our co-workers. Ask for help because don't act tough if you can't handle it because</p>

Engaging to Self- Care and Stress Relief Strategies	<p>you'll really get stressed out.” – IDI12</p> <p>“So, what I do is just find ways to unwind. Then, I watch some anime. I just scroll through Facebook, leave it for a few minutes, and then come back. And also, just eat if there's plenty of money.” – IDI07</p> <p>“One of the things that helps me manage my stress is giving my students performance tasks. Like, for example, I'm teaching mathematics, but sometimes we have role-playing activities. So, I enjoy watching their acts. It's like they make me laugh, so it relieves stress.” – IDI08</p> <p>“I eat a lot and it relieves my stress. And then, I just keep watching YouTube.” – IDI09</p> <p>“I watch movies when I feel stressed. And I also read motivational quotes to avoid getting too stressed out.” – IDI13</p> <p>“Okay, in handling stress, I just eat when I'm stressed. I also like to watch movies to relax. And sometimes sleeping.” – IDI14</p>
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Finding Inspiration to Teach by Students' Enthusiasm for Learning

The theme focuses on the inspiration of the teachers during the experience in teaching mathematics, despite being a non-mathematics major teacher. The participants highlight the things or people that inspires them to keep going despite the challenges they have encountered in their journey on teaching mathematics.

Moreover, their inspirations really push them to keep going even though they struggle to effectively deliver difficult math terms and explanations during teaching. According to Joyful (pseudonym), he said that he does not have any choice because there is no one else to do the job. He also said that the kids or the learners are the one that keeps motivating him. Despite of the hardness of the subject, he still continues to teach because of his learners. He stated that:

“Kinahanglan jud naay math teacher kay wala may laing mudawat (nikatawa). Mao nang nitudlo ko. Pero, na motivate pud ko sa mga bata kay sa pag tuo nako nga kanang kinahanglan jud ni sa mga bata, inig abot sa panahon.” – (IDI01)

(“You know, it's like, someone has to be the math teacher because there's no one else to do it (laughs). That's why I teach. But I also get motivated by the kids because I believe it's really necessary for them, especially in the long run.”)

In addition, Writer (pseudonym), he said that the eagerness of the student is what makes him motivated to teach. The students are the ones who is making him love his job more, because he is happy when he sees him students crave for more learnings coming from him. He stated that:

“First is, ahh kahit dili pa klase noh, dili pa klase pag masugatan nako akong mga students, “sir, unsa napud atong mga topic karon?” “unsa napud atong lesson karon?”. Kase, they enjoy while learning. Kana lang, that's one of the strategies, teaching strategies na gina implement nako. For them to love learning mathematics. So, kadto lang naka motivate sa akoo. Eagerness sa mga learners” (IDI04)

(“Firstly, even before class starts, when my students ask me, “Sir, what's our topic for today?” or “What's our lesson for today?” it shows that they enjoy learning. That's one of the teaching strategies I implement—to make them love learning mathematics. So, that's what motivates me. The eagerness of the learners.”)

Additionally, Chill (pseudonym) really point out that what motivates him is his students, especially those who do not see how enjoyable math can be. His inspiration is really effective, because of course it does really have some students that see mathematics as a boring subject and a hard one. So, this inspiration really matters. He stated:

“Students. Students that are not kanang, wala nila Nakita kung unsa ka lami ang mathematics. So, ang motivation is ang studyante ug ang ilahang mga learnings nga makuha sa akoo.” (IDI05)

(Students. Students who haven't seen how enjoyable mathematics can be. So, motivation comes from the students and their learning that they get from me.)

Furthermore, Soft Voice (pseudonym) also stated that, what really motivates her is seeing her students learning from her, and not just going to school to pass time. Because she really wants to make her students become successful in the future, she stated:

“Personally, what motivates me to keep going is kuan, I can see that my students are learning, and I know that they are not just there you know, they went to school to learn I want my students to be successful, at the same time I want them to be part of a society nga loving.” (IDI- 08)

(Personally, what motivates me to keep going is seeing that my students are learning and knowing that they are not just there to pass time. I want my students to succeed and become contributing members of a loving society.)

Lastly, Angel (pseudonym) expressed that her main motivation is also her students. She always remembers that her students always rely on her, that is why she is keep going despite the difficulty of the subject, she said:

“Okay, so the main motivation why I keep going even though teaching math is very hard, is my students. Why? My students are just relying on me. They are waiting for me to teach them new lessons for them to learn.” (IDI- 14)

(Okay, so the main motivation for why I keep going even though teaching math is very hard, is my students. Why? Because my students rely on me. They are waiting for me to teach them new lessons for them to learn.)

Preparing Diverse Resources for Student Engagement

The theme focuses on the preparations of the teachers before going in or starting to teach to their students in the classroom, despite being a non-mathematics major teacher. The participants highlight the things that they do to keep being prepared when teaching to their learners. Moreover, their preparations really helped them to keep going even though they struggle to effectively deliver difficult math terms and explanations during teaching, but they still manage to teach it to their students really well. According to Scientist (pseudonym), she said that she constantly utilizes PowerPoint presentations and video lessons, especially on those topics that are challenging to explain. She stated that:

“Okay, so in mathematics I always do PowerPoint presentation, and kaning mga video lesson. Labi nag kanang topic nga maglisod kog explain on my own. So, magpalaban kog video lesson.” (IDI-10)

(Alright, in mathematics, I consistently utilize PowerPoint presentations and video lessons, especially for topics that are challenging to explain solely through verbal explanation. I find that incorporating video lessons helps to reinforce the concepts effectively.)

As with the other participant, Dynamic (pseudonym) stated that he studies his topics every day before class, even weekends. He also said that he used to watch tutorials and search his topics on the internet. This preparation is really an effective way when we are teaching the subjects that is not our field. He stated:

“Okay, I study my topics every day before class, even weekends. I used to watch YouTube videos, like tutorials and search my topics on the internet, aside from the books and modules we had.” (IDI-11)

(Okay, I study my topics every day before class, even weekends. I used to watch YouTube videos, like tutorials and search my topics on the internet, aside from the books and modules we had.)

Moreover, engaging activities such as collaborative learning also can help in preparing and learning more about the topics, according to Caring (pseudonym). She said that to be more prepared, the approach should be more student-centered so the students can retain the concepts better, she said:

“Most of the time, dapat naa jud tay mga engaging activities such as collaborative learnings, noh. Dapat kanang more on student-centered ang kanang kuan kay para maka experience sila or ma retain sa ilahang huna- huna nga ing-ana diay.” (IDI-12)

(Most of the time, we should have engaging activities such as collaborative learning. The approach should be more student-centered so they can experience and retain the concepts better.)

Furthermore, Serious (pseudonym) expressed that the preparations he does includes studying the lesson, preparing the materials that will be used, prepare the lesson plan, and organize the activities before going to class. This kind of preparation really helps each teacher for the better of both learnings of the learners and also for himself to be able to teach effectively. He stated:

“Okay, so preparations of course ang akoang itudlo sa ilaha, akong ginastudigan nako akoang itudlo. Tapos, gina prepare pud nako ang mga materials nga akoang gamiton sa pagtudlo. And also, sa kanang mga examples nga akoang ipanghatag, akoo siyang gina studihan, gina answeran daan. Kay basin mangutana akong mga students, giunsa na, giunsa ni, ana makatubag ko. And para mas makasabot jud sila sa klase or kanang, or kanang makasabot jud sila. Kay naka prepare naman ko sa akoang lesson plan akoo pud ng gina prepare ahead before ko mag mag tudlo or a week before sa akoang klase, gina prepare najud nako akoang lesson plan. Tapos, along with the activities akoo napung gina han-ay kung unsang mga activities akoang gamiton sa pagtudlo aning lesson or ana nga topic.” (IDI-13)

(Okay, so preparations include studying the lesson I'll be teaching them. I thoroughly study what I'll teach them. Then, I also prepare the materials I'll use for teaching. I also ensure that my lesson plan is ready, usually preparing it a week before the class. Along with the activities, I organize what activities I'll use for teaching that particular lesson or topic.)

Lastly, Angel (pseudonym) expressed her preparations which also includes studying her topics every day. Additionally, she reviews the modules beforehand and also search her topics on the internet. This way of preparing before teaching was necessary because it can significantly help her to elaborate on the concepts of math, even though she is not a mathematics major, she mentioned:

“Preparations, so I study my topics every day, every night before my class, especially weekends kay mas taas ko ug time to study. I watched video tutorials on YouTube videos and search my topics on the internet. Also, we have modules that time, so I study before I enter my classroom for me to be prepared on what to discuss. Another one, we have our lesson plans man, so mao pud na isa sa akong preparations before I engaged in class.” (IDI-14)

(Preparations involve studying my topics every day, especially at night before my class, and particularly on weekends when I have more time to study. I watch video tutorials on YouTube and search for my topics on the internet. Additionally, I review the modules beforehand to ensure I'm prepared for what to discuss in class. Another aspect is preparing my lesson plans before I engage in class.)

Adapting and Consulting References to Improve Teaching Mathematics

The theme focuses on non-mathematics major teachers adapting to the teaching styles in mathematics and seeking guidance and support from cooperating teachers who is major in math to enhance their teaching skills and learnings, particularly in the context of teaching mathematics. The participants acknowledge the importance of knowing the basics of the lessons so that they can step up if they understand the concept of the topics. They recognize their co-teachers as valuable sources of feedback, constructive remarks, insights, and strategies to enhance their learning and instructional skills about the subject. Moreover, seeking guidance from experienced educators helps these teachers develop their teaching styles, learning, improve their ability to explain concepts, and enhance their overall thinking and teaching skills.

During the interview, Writer (pseudonym) said that he did not have any difficulty in adapting since he is an educator. He also stated that an educator is always open and will not just stay inside the box, because change is constant, he shared:

“Uhm, wala ko naglisod sa pag adapt since educator man ta noh. So, gikaingon pud na changes is the constant thing. So, open jud ta ana. Dili jud ta muingon nga, we'll just be inside this box.” (IDI04)

(“I didn't have difficulty in adapting since we're educators, right? So, it's also said that changes are constant. So, we're open to that. We won't just say, we'll just stay inside this box.”)

In addition, Dynamic (pseudonym) expressed that his preparation involves studying and consulting various references. He also believed that if there is something that he cannot grasp easily, then he will seek help to those experts, those who major in math, he stated:

“So ang preparations nako is study. Unya a lot of references. And then pag naa jud koy dili masabtan, daghan kog mapangutan-an nga mga major in math najud. Kanang mga expert-expert najud.” (IDI05)

(My preparation involves studying and consulting various references. If there's something I can't grasp, I ask those who are majoring in math, the experts.)

Moreover, Soft Voice (pseudonym) sought guidance from her cooperating teacher to enhance learning and teaching skills in teaching mathematics. Particularly, she relied on the expertise of Sir Fred, who instructed her on some of the strategies on how to deliver well the topic. The cooperating teacher played a pivotal role in assisting her in improving her teaching strategies, specifically within the context of teaching mathematics. The guidance and support provided by the teacher significantly contributed to Soft Voice's (pseudonym) overall development and adaptation in teaching mathematics, she stated:

“As first time nga non-mathematics teacher teaching mathematics. Kanang giunsa nako pag adapt, I think along the way ma learn lang gyud nimo. And at the same time with the help of your co-teachers, kase I am always asking Sir Fred, which is a mathematics jud nga major. So naga ask ko niya nga “sir unsaon kuni pag deliver? Kaning mga variables and constant direa sa algebraic expression?” “So, unsay nice nga examples ani?” , so hatagan rapud kog tips ni sir. So, along the way, na adapt lang nako, ah ingon ani diay.” (IDI-08)

(As a first-time non-mathematics teacher teaching mathematics, adapting was a learning process along the way. With the help of my co-teachers, especially Sir Fred, who is a mathematics major, I would ask him questions like, 'Sir, how should I deliver this? What are some nice examples for these variables and constants in algebraic expressions?' He would give me tips. So, I adapted gradually through this process.)

Furthermore, Scientist (pseudonym) shared her experience of seeking support and advice from his cooperating teachers. By reaching out to these experienced professionals, she was able to gain valuable insights, receive constructive feedback, and obtain helpful suggestions to enhance her learnings and in the context of teaching mathematics. It helps her to make the burden becomes lighter and makes her less stress. This collaborative approach not only allowed Scientist (pseudonym) to improve her teaching abilities but also fostered a supportive and enriching environment within the educational community, she mentioned:

“Kuan, mag ask kog help sa other teachers nga mga, sa pareha direa naa may math major isa, so kung stress na kaayo ko kay wako kabalo ani, muadto ko sa iyaha, mag magpatabang ko nga “Cha, unsaon mani uy diko kabalo”. So, sa iyaha mag ask kog help para mas mu kuan ang burden, nya di na nako siya ma stress, di na nako ma stress ana nga topic, kay nakasabot ra. So, ing- ana. Kanang, I am asking the help of my colleague.” (IDI-10)

(I ask for help from other teachers, especially those who are math majors like me. If I'm feeling very stressed because I don't know how to handle something, I go to them and say, 'Hey, can you help me with this? I'm not sure what to do.' I ask for their help so that the burden becomes lighter, and I no longer stress about that topic because I now understand. I seek the assistance of my colleague.)

In his teaching journey, Dynamic (pseudonym) sought guidance and assistance from his colleagues. These individuals played a pivotal role in enhancing Dynamic's (pseudonym) teaching skills and overall improvement as a teacher, he stated:

“I always ask questions or advise to some of my colleagues that is expert in mathematics. I am open to any suggestions, clarifications, and comments from my colleagues.” (IDI-11)

(I always ask questions or advise to some of my colleagues that is expert in mathematics. I am open to any suggestions, clarifications, and comments from my colleagues.)

Lastly, Caring (pseudonym) expressed her need for assistance, particularly from her colleagues. She believed that there is no wrong in asking for help. Seeking help from others can help so that no stress may occur. She said that we should not act tough if you really cannot handle the topics because you will get stresses out. Therefore, she sought guidance from her co-workers, specifically asking for help in choosing the appropriate strategy for the next topic, she shared:

“Unya sometimes kanang as a non-math major, unya specially ma stress ka sa topic, you can go to your mga co-teachers nga kanang math major. Pwede man ka magpa tabang para di ka ma stress ug unsaon na siya, unsaon mana siya pag deliver sa imuhang learners. So, magayo tag, dili man dautan nga mangayo ug tabang sa atoang co-workers. So, pangayo ug tabang, kay ayaw pagpa hawd-hawd kung dijud nimo kaya kay ma stress rajud ka ana.” (IDI-12)

(I ask for help from other teachers, especially those who are math majors like me. You can ask for help so that you won't stress about how to deliver it to your learners. So, let's seek, let's ask for help, it's not bad to seek help from our co-workers. Ask for help because don't act tough if you can't handle it because you'll really get stressed out.)

Engaging to Self-Care and Stress Relief Strategies

The theme talks about the importance of self-care and what strategies these non-mathematics major teachers do have to relief their stress along the experiences they have during teaching mathematics.

The participants emphasize the need to unwind, eat a lot, watching movies, and sometimes sleeping for them to feel relaxed. By these, teachers now forget the problems that occurs during teaching, the stress when they handled different students with different attitudes along with the subject that is not in their field. During the interview, Pretty (pseudonym) stated that what she just do is to find a way to unwind, watch anime, and also eat. She said:

“So, gikuan lang nako kanang mag unwind, charot. Tapos ano mag tan-aw-tan-aw lang kog ano mga anime. Mag scroll lang ko sa facebook, pasagdaan sa tika diraa mga pila ka minutes ah balikan napud tika. Tapos ano pud kato lang, mag kaon-kaon if naay daghang kwarta.” (IDI07)

(So, what I do is just find ways to unwind. Then, I watch some anime. I just scroll through Facebook, leave it for a few minutes, and then come back. And also, just eat if there's plenty of money.)

As with the other participant, Soft Voice (pseudonym) shared that her way in relieving her stress is to give her students task to which it can help her to become happy. It is an engaging activity, as well as it can also help vanished her stress. These activity includes, role-playing, she shared:

“So, one of the things nga makapamanage sa akong stress is kuan, kanang ginahatagan nako ug mga performance task akong mga students. Like for example, I'm teaching mathematics noh, pero naa mi role play usahay. So pag malingaw ko sa ilahang mga act ba. So, murag makapakatawa sa akoa, so maka wala siya 'g stress.” (IDI-08)

(One of the things that helps me manage my stress is giving my students performance tasks. Like, for example, I'm teaching mathematics, but sometimes we have role-playing activities. So, I enjoy watching their acts. It's like they make me laugh, so it relieves stress.)

In addition, Achiever (pseudonym) shared that her way of relieving her stress is through eating and watching YouTube. By doing these, it can help her relax her mind and forget her stress, she said:

“Siguro kuan lang, mukaon raman pud ko haha ug ma stress ko. And then magsige lang ko ug kuan tan aw sa YouTube.” (IDI-09)

(I eat a lot and it relieves my stress. And then, I just keep watching YouTube.)

Moreover, Serious (pseudonym) pointed out that also watched movies when he feels stressed. Additionally, he mentioned that he would also read motivational quotes, he shared:

“Nagatan-aw ko ug mga ah movie pag ma stress ko. Tapos, ano ug kanang magbasa-basa ug kanang motivational quotes aron dili lang gud kaayo ma stress” (IDI-13)

(I watch movies when I feel stressed. And I also read motivational quotes to avoid getting too stressed out.)

Lastly, Angel (pseudonym) also stated that in handling stress, she just eat a lot, and she likes to watch movies, and also she sleeps, she stated:

“Okay, in handling stress, I just eat lang man pag stress ko uy. I also like to watch movies para mahuwasan ko. And sometimes matulog pud diay.” (IDI-14)

(Okay, in handling stress, I just eat when I'm stressed. I also like to watch movies to relax. And sometimes sleeping.)

Research Question No. 3: What insights can be obtained from these non- mathematics major teachers teaching mathematics that can be shared to other mathematics teachers and to the academe in general?

To answer this research question, in-depth interviews were conducted with the participants, respectively. Hence, several sub-questions were asked to understand their experiences regarding the language they used in mathematics teaching.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 3 were presented in Table 4. From the answers of the participants, six major themes had emerged: embrace growth through learning and adaptation, teaching requires mutual effort from both teachers and students, remain flexible and adaptable, stay resilient and determined amidst challenges, find joy in teaching and value in teaching mathematics, and implementation of trainings and seminars.

Table 4. Insights of the Non-Mathematics Major Teacher Teaching Mathematics

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Embrace Growth through Learning and Adaptation	<p>“For me, the lessons I've learned in teaching this, is about accepting responsibility, you know, accepting whatever is given by the school head, just accepting it.” – IDI-1</p> <p>“Ah, you embrace what's given to you. So, the lessons are, accept. Accept all the challenges, don't give up. Especially in the field of work, especially in teaching, we shouldn't give up.” – IDI-4</p> <p>“So, we cannot deny the fact that it's difficult. There are times when it's hard, but the lesson is, like I mentioned earlier, things can be learned. So, if you are an open-minded person, if you are willing to learn, things can be learned. Even if it's not your field, even if it's not your thing, but if you have the will to learn new things, you can learn them along the way.” – IDI- 9</p> <p>“The lesson is you must be versatile, not just focusing on one aspect. Because if you're there, stuck in Aral- Pan, you should not just be in Aral-Pan. You need to adapt, or you need to embrace other subjects as well.” – IDI-12</p> <p>“Okay, one of the things I learned from my experience as a non-mathematics teacher is not to be stagnant in just focusing on your major or on the subjects you find easy. You should also be able to explore other subjects. We should know how to adapt to whatever is given to us, like when I was given the math subject even though it wasn't my field or major.” – IDI-13</p>
Teaching Requires Mutual Effort from Both Teachers and Students	<p>“So, that's it. Learning is a two-way process.” – IDI-13</p> <p>“Well, it takes two to tango, you know, that both the teacher and the student need to make an effort for harmony.” – IDI-8</p> <p>“So, this is really the life of a teacher. It's difficult, but when you see your students listening, and you can also see that they're willing to learn as much as you're willing as a teacher, you'll really be motivated to enjoy what you're doing.” – IDI-9</p> <p>“As a teacher, we need to be flexible, that's why we just accept it.” – IDI-1</p> <p>“Being versatile or flexible enough is one of the characteristics or qualities I've gained, the lesson I've learned from teaching this subject, math.” – IDI-2</p> <p>“We shouldn't just be stagnant, we should also be flexible, like that.” – IDI-7</p> <p>“They say teachers are versatile. Even in our characterizations, we are also versatile.” – IDI-8</p>
Remain Flexible and Adaptable	<p>“The lesson is you must be versatile, not just focusing on one aspect. Don't limit yourself to one place. You must break out of your box.” – IDI-12</p> <p>“I suggest to all teachers to be flexible all the time, because we are teachers, we shouldn't just complain.” – IDI-14</p>
Stay Resilient and Determined Amidst Challenges	<p>“Keep fighting! My inspiring words are, let's not surrender.” – IDI-1</p> <p>“Go on. Don't refuse if you're given mathematics tasks, even if you're not a mathematics major... if it's given to you, just accept it and stop complaining.” – IDI-4</p> <p>“Just get up, do your job, and everything will be fine.” – IDI-8</p> <p>“Is 'keep fighting' inspiring enough? Just keep fighting! And continue the fire of your passion, and then continue teaching the students, not only from the mind, but also from the heart.” – IDI-9</p> <p>“Okay, we can do it! We can do it because we're teachers, we're flexible.” – IDI-10</p> <p>“The inspiring words that I can give to non- mathematics teachers is to keep fighting. And never give up, never surrender to your students.” – IDI-13</p> <p>“Inspiring words, we can do this! Just keep fighting!” – IDI-14</p>
Find Joy in Teaching and Value in Teaching Mathematics	<p>“Love your work. Just love your work, because that's what you're doing from the moment you start working.” – IDI-3</p> <p>“Just be happy because mathematics is fun.” – IDI-5</p> <p>“Math is really good to study, to teach, and to adapt to the learnings related to it.” – IDI-6</p> <p>“I used to think back in elementary until high school that I couldn't love math. Then, when I was taught it, that's when I realized that math is really nice because it can be used every day.” – IDI-7</p> <p>“We encounter a lot of things in the teaching profession. Because what you realize is that when your learners have learned, it's really fulfilling to see that they've learned from you. And at the same time, that can be a basis for you to strive harder, because you know that you've imparted something to them.” – IDI-12</p>
Implementation of Trainings and Seminars	<p>“Perhaps in mathematics, they would undergo training in mathematics or whatever training is needed to sharpen their skills in mathematics before they start teaching it.” – IDI-1</p> <p>“If there are non-math teachers who are willing to teach math, they should undergo seminars first. Then, they</p>

should undergo training, like that, to gain some knowledge and background.” – IDI-7
 “If you are not a mathematics major but are teaching mathematics, you are encouraged to attend trainings and seminars related to math, so that at least you will be more aware of developments because there are also changes in the curriculum.” – IDI-12

Embrace Growth through Learning and Adaptation

The theme emphasizes how the teachers embrace and adapt the subject mathematics. It highlights that as a teacher, you really need to become versatile and be open to new learnings, by embracing what comes to you. Moreover, by embracing the things that you are not good into, may become your new key to new goods things in life. By embracing growth through learning and adaptation, teachers can enhance their ability to explain and elaborate on mathematical concepts, ensure student comprehension, and promptly address any difficulties or concern effectively. During the interview, Joyful (pseudonym) emphasized the lessons that he learned through teaching math is about accepting responsibility, accepting what the school head gave to you, he said:

“Para sa akong ang lessons nga akong nahibal an sa pagtudlo ani, kay mudawat jud sa responsibilidad kung unsay unsa na ihatag sa school head, mudawat lang jud ta.” (IDI01)

(IDI1- “For me, the lessons I've learned in teaching this, is about accepting responsibility, you know, accepting whatever is given by the school head, just accepting it.”)

As with the other participant, Writer (pseudonym) stated that in the field of education or in teaching, we should just embrace what is given to us. He said that the lesson is just to accept all the challenges in teaching, especially in the field of work, he said:

“Ah, kumabaga e hug nimo ang gihatag sa imo. So, mga lessons is, accept. Accept all the challenges, dili ka magpakasayon. In the field of work, lalong lalo na yung teaching is dili ta magpakasayon noh.” (IDI04)

(“Ah, you embrace what's given to you. So, the lessons are, accept. Accept all the challenges, don't give up. Especially in the field of work, especially in teaching, we shouldn't give up.”)

In addition, Achiever (pseudonym) shared that math is really difficult, but for her, if you have the will to learn, if you have a mind that is open for new learning, then the hardness of the subject is not a hindrance. Because according to her, things can just be learned along the way, she shared:

“So we cannot deny the fact na kanang, lisod siya. Naay times na mag lisod ka, pero lessons no kay, sama sa akong giingon ganina kay, things can be learned gyud. So, kanang kung if you are just, if you are an open- minded person, if you are willing to learn, things can be learned jud, things can be learned. Bisan pa 'g dili nimo na siya field, dili nimo na siya thing, but if you have the kanang, the kana ganing will to learn new things, ma learn ragyud na nimo siya, along the way” (IDI-09)

(So, we cannot deny the fact that it's difficult. There are times when it's hard, but the lesson is, like I mentioned earlier, things can be learned. So, if you are an open- minded person, if you are willing to learn, things can be learned. Even if it's not your field, even if it's not your thing, but if you have the will to learn new things, you can learn them along the way.)

Moreover, Caring (pseudonym) emphasized by being a teacher, you have to become versatile. You should not only focus on one aspect, but you also need to embrace other subject as well for your grow, she said:

“Lesson is you must be versatile, dili lang ka mag focus sa isa ka aspect. Dili kay kung diha ka, Aral-Pan ka diha lang jud ka sa Aral-Pan. You need to adapt, or you need to embrace kanang other pud nga mga subject.” (IDI-12)

(The lesson is you must be versatile, not just focusing on one aspect. Because if you're there, stuck in Aral- Pan, you should not just be in Aral-Pan. You need to adapt, or you need to embrace other subjects as well.)

Lastly, Serious (pseudonym) also said that by being a teacher, you should not be stagnant. You should explore other subjects and that you should know how to adapt to whatever subject that is given to you.

By this, you can now teach other subjects too and you will learn new things because of it. And if another opportunity is given to you, then you will not be scared anymore because you have now the experience. In her statement, she shared:

“Okay so isa jud sa akoang na learn sa akong mga experience as a non-mathematics teacher is kanang dili lang ka stagnant sa kung unsa nga major ka, or sa unsa nga subject lang ka hawd. Dapat kabalo pud ka mu explore ug other subject, pareha aning math nga gihatag sa akong, wala kaayo ko ga kuan ani ga study gyud all the time sa pagskwela nako. So, kato siya nga nakatuon ko nga mas nindot gyud diay magtuon ug other subjects nga kanang wala nimo gi skwelahan kay para magamit pato nimo kung magtudlo naka puhon tapos e assign ka sa kana nga field or subject.” (IDI-13)

(Okay, one of the things I learned from my experience as a non-mathematics teacher is not to be stagnant in just focusing on your major or on the subjects you find easy. You should also be able to explore other subjects. We should know how to adapt to whatever is given to us, like when I was given the math subject even though it wasn't my field or major.)

Teaching Requires Mutual Effort from Both Teachers and Students

The theme explores the importance of mutual effort from both teachers and students, particularly in mathematics lessons or in teaching mathematics. The participants, who are non-mathematics major teachers, emphasizes that in a classroom or in teaching, it is important that the teacher and the students have mutual understanding, so that the learnings are smoother. Since both of the parties may acquire knowledge from each other. The theme underscores the idea that mutual understanding towards the teacher and students is crucial in ensuring that students comprehend the subject matter that the teacher teach, and that the teacher also learn and know effectively the subject matter that he/she taught to his/her students. During the interview, Traditional (pseudonym) stated that learning is indeed a two-way process, she said:

“So, kana siya. Learning is ano, a two-way process.” (IDI03)

(“So, that’s it. Learning is a two-way process.”)

As with the other participant, Soft Voice (pseudonym) also said that it takes two to tango. To make the learning process more effective, the student and the teacher must do things to creative harmony, she stated:

“Then siguro it takes two to tango, na kailangan ninyo mag effort both the teacher and the student. For you to have harmony gyud.” (IDI-08)

(Well, it takes two to tango, you know, that both the teacher and the student need to make an effort for harmony.)

Lastly, Achiever (pseudonym) said that the life of a teacher is really difficult, but when you see your students willing to learn from you, you will be motivated to push through your journey teaching, despite the challenge that it is not your major subject. It is really true that if you saw your students’ willingness to learn, then you will have more power to teach them. That is why, mutual understanding between the teacher and the students really matters. In her statement, she said:

“Ing ani gyud diay ang life sa teacher haha. Lisod siya pero pag makita nimo imong mga studyante nga kanang maminaw, makita pud nimo nga kanang willing pud sila mu learn as much as how willing you are as a teacher, ma acquire ragyud nimo nga maganahan rapud ka sa imong ginahimo.” (IDI-09)

(So, this is really the life of a teacher. It's difficult, but when you see your students listening, and you can also see that they're willing to learn as much as you're willing as a teacher, you'll really be motivated to enjoy what you're doing.)

Remain Flexible and Adaptable

The theme explores that the teachers are not stagnant. Teachers are flexible and versatile. The participants, who are non-mathematics major teachers, emphasizes that teachers can do anything. Teachers don’t complain. Teachers can ace anything, even though it is not their field. The theme underscores the idea that teachers really are the ones who do not say no and can easily adapt anything. During the interview, Joyful (pseudonym) stated that teachers really need to be flexible. That is why he just easily accept the challenge of his school head to teach subject that is not aligned with his field, he said:

“As a teacher we need to be flexible, mao na nga dawad sa dawad lang” (IDI01)

(“As a teacher, we need to be flexible, that's why we just accept it.”)

As with the other participant, Happy (pseudonym) stated that one of the characters that she gained throughout teaching mathematics is being flexible and versatile. This indicates that, teachers really are flexible towards anything, she shared:

“Being versatile or flexible enough. Being flexible is one of the character or qualities that I’ve gained, the lesson that I’ve learned teaching this, the subject math.” (IDI02)

(Being versatile or flexible enough is one of the characteristics or qualities I've gained, the lesson I've learned from teaching this subject, math.)

In addition, Pretty (pseudonym) also stated that teachers really should not become stagnant. There are many ways on how someone especially teacher can be productive and learn new things. A person should not be stuck into one place. If ever you master that one thing, then it is time for you to learn new things. In her statement, she said:

“Ayaw pud kanang, dapat dili lang stagnant no, dapat flexible pud, ingon-ana.” (IDI07)

(We shouldn't just be stagnant, we should also be flexible, like that.)

Furthermore, Soft Voice (pseudonym) also tells that there is really a character in a specific teacher that is versatile, she stated:

“So, kanang ingon sila nga teachers are versatile. Even in our characterization, murag versatile pud ta.” (IDI-08)

(They say teachers are versatile. Even in our characterizations, we are also versatile.)

Additionally, a teacher should not limit him/herself into one place. Thus, a teacher must break out of its box, according to Caring (pseudonym). A teacher should not only focus into one aspect, but he/she also must learn to adapt and accept new things, she shared:

“Kuan jud siya you must be versatile jud. Dili lang ka dapat mag focus sa isa lang ka subject matter. Kay, kung dira ka perminte, dili jud ka mulabmo. So, you must be versatile in any aspect, especially in teaching, kay para you will grow more. Dili lang ah personal, ah dili lang kanang kumbaga is kanang dili lang ka ma lansang sa isa lang ka lugar. So, you must be muhawa or mu out, mu out ka sa imohang box noh.” (IDI-12)

(The lesson is you must be versatile, not just focusing on one aspect. Don't limit yourself to one place. You must break out of your box.)

Lastly, Angel (pseudonym) suggest that teachers really need to be flexible at all times. Teachers should not complain because it is their duty to serve the students new learnings. Things can be learned along the way; it is just that the person needs to be willing to learn. In her statement, she said:

“I suggest to all teachers nga be flexible all the time, because we are teachers man, dili nalang ta mag reklamo.” (IDI-14)

(I suggest to all teachers to be flexible all the time, because we are teachers, we shouldn't just complain.)

Stay Resilient and Determined Amidst Challenges

This theme emphasizes the inspiring words that the teachers want to tell and share to other non-mathematics teacher who teaches math, or to those teachers who teaches something that is not in their field. During the interview, Joyful (pseudonym) wants to tell other teachers to keep fighting, and not surrender, he said:

“Laban lang! Bitaw akong mga inspiring words is, kanang dili lang ta musurrender.” (IDI01)

(“Keep fighting! My inspiring words are, let's not surrender.”)

As with the other participant, Writer (pseudonym) wanted to say to other teachers that, if you are given a math task even if you are not a mathematics major, just accept it and do not complain. Just go on, because a teacher can do anything and you just need to accept and embrace it, he shared:

“Go on. Ayaw balibad kung hatagan ka ug mathematics, although dili ka mathematics major So, ug gihatag na sa imuha, be it and ayaw na sigeg reklamo.” (IDI04)

(Go on. Don't refuse if you're given mathematics tasks, even if you're not a mathematics major. If it's given to you, just accept it and stop complaining.)

In addition, Soft Voice (pseudonym) wanted to say that if you are a teacher who teaches a subject that is not inline in your field, just get up because you can do it. Do your job, because you are a teacher. And always remember that everything will be fine, just give your best shot. In her statement, she said:

“Get up and kuan lang, get up, do your job, and everything will be fine lang jud” (IDI-08)

(Just get up, do your job, and everything will be fine.)

Furthermore, Achiever (pseudonym) wanted to say that if you are a teacher who teaches a subject that is not inline in your field, just keep fighting. Just continue to teach your students and do it not only from your mind but also from your heart. Continue the fire of your passion within you, she shared:

“Ah inspiring words, inspiring ban ang laban lang? Laban lang ta! And then, continue the fire sa imong passion, and then continue teaching the students, not only from the mind, but also from the heart.” (IDI-09)

(Is 'keep fighting' inspiring enough? Just keep fighting! And continue the fire of your passion, and then continue teaching the students, not only from the mind, but also from the heart.)

Moreover, Scientist (pseudonym) wanted to say to other teachers that they can do it. They can definitely do it, because they are a teacher. In phrase "we can do it" underscores a sense of optimism and self-assurance. She believes in their own capabilities and those of their colleagues. By stating "we're flexible," she emphasizes a crucial characteristic of teachers. Flexibility here suggests the ability to adapt to changing circumstances, embrace new methods, and respond to unexpected situations effectively. Overall, the statement embodies a resilient and adaptable mindset, which is essential for educators who often face dynamic and unpredictable environments, she said:

“Okay, kaya natin to! We can do it! Kay teacher man ta, flexible ta.” (IDI-10)

(Okay, we can do it! We can do it because we're teachers, we're flexible.)

Additionally, Serious (pseudonym) also emphasizes a message of perseverance and resilience that should be aimed, particularly to

those who do not teach mathematics. He aims to uplift and motivate non-mathematics teachers by urging them to continue their efforts despite any challenges they may face. He also highlights the importance of maintaining authority and dedication in the classroom. This phrase can be interpreted as encouraging teachers to stand firm in their educational mission, to uphold high standards, and to continuously support and challenge their students without yielding to frustration or giving up. Overall, the statement serves as a rallying cry for teachers to remain resolute and committed to their profession, reinforcing the idea that perseverance and dedication are crucial attributes in the face of adversity, he shared:

“Okay so inspiring words nga akong mahatag rajud noh sa mga non-mathematics teachers is, laban lang jud. And never give up, never surrender sa imong mga students.” (IDI-13)

(The inspiring words that I can give to non-mathematics teachers is to keep fighting. And never give up, never surrender to your students.)

Lastly, Angel (pseudonym) reflects a positive mindset by stating that they can do it. She is instilling confidence and a belief in their collective ability to overcome challenges. She also emphasizes the importance of persistence and resilience. It encourages continuous effort and determination, even in the face of difficulties. Overall, the statement is a motivational call to action, urging individuals or a group to stay united, remain positive, and persist in their efforts despite any obstacles they may encounter, she said:

“Inspiring words umm, kaya natin to! Laban lang!” (IDI- 14)

(IDI14- “Inspiring words, we can do this! Just keep fighting!”)

Find Joy in Teaching and Value in Teaching Mathematics

The theme emphasizes the importance and significance of teaching mathematics. It calls on educators to recognize the value and impact that math education has on students' overall academic development and future opportunities. Moreover, it encourages educators to seek and embrace the intrinsic rewards and satisfaction that come from teaching. It highlights the importance of recognizing and appreciating the positive aspects of the profession, such as inspiring students, witnessing their growth, and the personal fulfillment derived from contributing to their learning journey.

During the interview, Joyful (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of having a genuine passion for what you do. It suggests that finding joy and satisfaction in your job is crucial for long-term fulfillment and success. It is highlighted that from the moment you begin working, your job becomes a significant part of your life. Loving your work ensures that this substantial portion of your time is spent in a positive and fulfilling manner, she said:

“Love your work. Love your work nalang, kay mao naman na, from the moment mao naman na imong gi trabaho.” (IDI03”

(“Love your work. Just love your work, because that's what you're doing from the moment you start working.”)

As with the other participant, Chill (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of maintaining a cheerful and optimistic mindset. He suggests that a positive attitude can enhance the learning and teaching experience. Emphasizing the fun aspect of mathematics can help in motivating students and making the subject more accessible and interesting. When students find joy in learning math, they are likely to be more engaged and enthusiastic. Overall, this statement is a call to approach mathematics with a sense of joy and enthusiasm, fostering a positive and enjoyable learning environment. It encourages both teachers and students to find the fun in mathematics, which can lead to a more engaging and effective educational experience, he shared:

“Just be happy. Just be happy because mathematics is fun.” (IDI05)

(Just be happy because mathematics is fun.)

In addition, Agronomist (pseudonym) emphasizes the significance of mathematics in the curriculum. It highlights the role of educators in imparting mathematical knowledge and fostering critical thinking, problem-solving, and analytical skills in students. Overall, this statement underscores the comprehensive benefits of mathematics in education, highlighting its importance in studying, teaching, and its adaptability to broader learning contexts. It encourages a recognition of the value that mathematics brings to both educators and learners, she shared:

“Nindot pud diay jud si math studihan, tudluan, ug mu adapt ka ug mga learnings nga related ani niya.” (IDI06)

(Math is really good to study, to teach, and to adapt to the learnings related to it.)

Furthermore, Pretty (pseudonym) reflects a personal journey and transformation in the perception of mathematics. She starts by acknowledging a common experience—struggling with or disliking math during the early school years. This sets the stage for a significant change in attitude. The turning point comes when she is taught math in a way that makes it understandable and relatable. This highlights the impact of effective teaching methods and the importance of educators in changing students' attitudes toward challenging subjects. Overall, this statement illustrates the potential for attitudes toward mathematics to change through effective teaching and the recognition of its practical uses. It emphasizes the importance of relatable and applied learning experiences in fostering a positive relationship with the subject, she shared:

“Abi nako sauna way back elementary hangtod high school nga dili nako ma love ang math. Then, tung gipatudlo na, didto nako na realize nga kanang nice kaayo si math kay magamit siya every day.” (IDI07)

(I used to think back in elementary until high school that I couldn't love math. Then, when I was taught it, that's when I realized that math is really nice because it can be used every day.)

Lastly, Caring (pseudonym) highlights the deep sense of fulfillment that comes from seeing students learn and grow. Knowing that students have gained knowledge and skills from their teaching is a significant source of satisfaction for educators. The realization that students have learned from their efforts serves as a motivation for teachers to strive harder. This continuous improvement is driven by the desire to have a positive impact on students' lives and to further enhance their teaching effectiveness. Overall, this statement emphasizes the rewarding nature of teaching, where the successes and learning achievements of students inspire teachers to keep improving and dedicating themselves to their profession. It highlights the cycle of fulfillment and motivation that sustains passionate and effective educators, she shared:

“Daghan man jud tag ma encounter no pag naa ta sa kuan, sa tawag ani sa teaching profession. Kay ang maka kuan sa imuha, makita gud nimo na kanang ang imuhang learners is naka learn or nay, lami man gud siya sa paminaw gud nga kanang nakita nimo ang imuhang learners nga naka kat-on sa imuha, at the same time murag kato siya ang murag mahimo nimong basis nga mas maningkamot pajud ka. Kay kanang kabalo man ka nga naa kay na impart sa ilaha.” (IDI-12)

(We encounter a lot of things in the teaching profession. Because what you realize is that when your learners have learned, it's really fulfilling to see that they've learned from you. And at the same time, that can be a basis for you to strive harder, because you know that you've imparted something to them.)

Implementation of Trainings and Seminars

The theme emphasizes the effective implementation of trainings and seminars in education that is crucial for fostering continuous professional development among educators. By strategically identifying needs, setting clear objectives, and delivering relevant content through engaging methods, institutions can empower teachers with practical knowledge and skills. This approach not only enhances teaching effectiveness but also cultivates a supportive learning environment where educators are motivated to innovate and adapt, ultimately benefiting student learning outcomes and the overall educational community.

During the interview, Joyful (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of teachers being well-prepared and competent in the subject they teach. This training is seen as essential for sharpening skills and building confidence before entering the classroom. By advocating for training to sharpen skills, the statement underscores a dedication to providing high-quality instruction in mathematics. It suggests a belief that well-trained teachers are better equipped to engage students, facilitate learning, and promote mathematical understanding. Loving your work ensures that this substantial portion of your time is spent in a positive and fulfilling manner, he said:

“Kung wala pay major in mathematics sa isa ka school, kinahanglan jud kung naay training, mu undergo sa ug training ang mga non-major teachers. Nga kuntahay mathematics, mu undergo sa sila ug training sa mathematics or unsa ba nga training kay para mahasa siya sa mathematics before siya mu tudlo ug mathematics” (IDI01)

(“Perhaps in mathematics, they would undergo training in mathematics or whatever training is needed to sharpen their skills in mathematics before they start teaching it.”)

In addition, Pretty (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of preparation and professional development for teachers transitioning into mathematics instruction. In her statement, she indicates a more intensive and structured educational program aimed at deepening understanding and competency in mathematics. This training is crucial for equipping non-math teachers with the necessary skills, methods, and content knowledge required for effective teaching. Overall, this advocates for a systematic and supportive pathway for non-math teachers who are interested in teaching mathematics, ensuring they receive adequate preparation and support through seminars and training. It reflects a commitment to quality education and professional growth, ultimately benefiting both teachers and students in the learning process, she mentioned:

“So, ako lang suggestion, dapat kung naa man mga, non-math teachers nga gusto nila ibutang sa nga magtudlo sa math, dapat seminar sa una. Then, mag undergo ug mga trainings, ingon-ana gud, para maka kuan man pud na ba, makahatag ug some knowledge man pud ug background.” (IDI07)

(If there are non-math teachers who are willing to teach math, they should undergo seminars first. Then, they should undergo training, like that, to gain some knowledge and background.)

Lastly, Caring (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of continuous professional development for educators teaching mathematics outside their primary field of study. The statement she said that to attend trainings and seminars related to math highlights the proactive approach to enhancing knowledge and skills in mathematics education. It encourages educators to seek opportunities for learning and staying updated with advancements in the field. The statement suggests that by attending these professional development opportunities, non-math majors can improve their ability to effectively teach mathematics. It supports the idea that continuous learning and professional growth contribute to better instructional practices and student learning outcomes. Overall, this statement promotes a culture

of lifelong learning among educators, encouraging them to invest in their professional development to better support students in mathematics education, despite not having a formal background in the subject. It underscores the importance of adaptation, growth, and responsiveness to evolving educational needs and standards, she mentioned:

“If you are not a mathematics major, and then you are teaching mathematics, you are encouraged to attend trainings and seminars nga related sa math, para at least you will be more aware sa mga panghitabo kay, naa man gud pud nay mga kabag-uhan, diba sa curriculum.” (IDI-12)

(If you are not a mathematics major but are teaching mathematics, you are encouraged to attend trainings and seminars related to math, so that at least you will be more aware of developments because there are also changes in the curriculum.)

Conclusions

In conclusion, the study concludes that the participants had variety of experiences that pointed to their challenges, stories of coping, and certain realizations about non-mathematics major teacher teaching mathematics. The findings reveal the complex challenges these educators face, as well as the strategies they employ to cope and the insights they have gained through their experiences.

Additionally, one of the key challenges highlighted is the difficulty in keeping up with the curriculum guide, especially those new ones. Non-mathematics teachers struggle to keep up with the new curriculum, and also to the topics that is new to them, along with the terminologies that is hard to understood. This difficulties that they faced often compromises their ability to fully focus on delivering effective lessons and supporting student learning.

However, the educators likewise exhibited wonderful flexibility and versatility. They have created procedures, for example, focusing on errands, using emotionally supportive networks, and esteeming their psychological and actual prosperity to explore the adequacy of their lessons. In addition, these experiences have given them the opportunity to expand their knowledge and abilities, boost their self-esteem, and develop a deeper appreciation for education and the students they teach.

In addition, seeking guidance from mentors, such as cooperating teachers or colleagues, is crucial for improving mathematical teaching skills and strategy in teaching mathematics. Their feedback and constructive remarks serve as new learnings and motivation to strive for better learning and proficiency in instruction. Additionally, watching videos, particularly on platforms like YouTube, is a resourceful strategy to develop solving mathematical problem and develop our logic and thinking skills and delivery techniques. These approaches collectively contribute to becoming more effective educators in conveying concepts.

In addition, I have encountered numerous challenges throughout my research journey, first is the finding of my participants. I traveled different municipalities around the Division of Davao del Norte just to find my participants. I even go to mountains and literally crossed a river. The second one lacks funding or budget for my research. This issue is compounded by the fact that I am a boarder and do not have my own WiFi, which means I have to spend money on network load every week or month in order to work on my research. Notwithstanding these difficulties, I'm earnestly appreciative to the Ruler God for giving me intelligence, information, and actual solidarity to endure with this review until its fruition.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Marjorie M. Moral

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology – Philippines

Elealeh S. Timosa, MAEd

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology – Philippines